

Please, to cite this article: García-Carmona, M., Fuentes-Mayorga, N. & Rodríguez-García, A. M. (2021). Educational Leadership for Social Justice in Multicultural Contexts: The Case of Melilla, Spain. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 20(1), 76-94, DOI: [10.1080/15700763.2020.1833939](https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2020.1833939)

Educational Leadership for Social Justice in Multicultural Contexts: The Case of Melilla, Spain

Marina García-Carmona ^a

^aFaculty of Education and Sport Sciences Faculty of Educational Sciences and Sport, Department of Didactics and School Organization, University of Granada, Melilla, Spain; ^bSociology Department and Latin American and Latina/o Studies, The City College of New York, City University of New York, New York, New York, USA

Abstract

In multicultural contexts, school principals and educators face unique challenges integrating disadvantaged and immigrant youth. We investigate how these leaders advocate, design and implement social justice pedagogies for inclusion. Drawing on an interdisciplinary literature and in-depth interviews with school principals in Melilla (Spain), we further explore the social justice ideologies and practices of leaders in culturally diverse, minority-majority schools. The findings reveal that intercultural education and ICT both enhance the inclusion of students and families, transforming schools into more open, democratic, learning environments. However, scarce funding resources, exacerbated by Melilla's remote location from its Central Ministry of Education and the limited bargaining power of leaders, often truncate social justice initiatives.

Introduction

Social justice leaders move beyond equality debates to equity debates, and set out to change systems, processes, and structures to better respond to the needs of students (Dantley & Tillman, 2006, p. 96)

As the above excerpt by leadership scholars Dantley and Tillman emphasizes, social justice in school settings rests on the hands of principals or educational leaders. An emerging literature reveals that in a changing, globalized knowledge economy, educational leaders play a preemptive role in preparing citizens who are culturally and technologically savvy and able to work in multicultural settings. Increasingly, school principals must move beyond debates of “equality” to practices of “equity,” which can address the changing needs of students in view of unprecedented immigration and demographic shifts. As this paper will reveal, nations and regions with historical legacies of immigration, like the case of Melilla (Spain) illustrates, may be more adept at designing social justice policies of inclusion for disadvantaged and migrant students but also for parents who lack knowledge about the expectations of the host school system (Alba & Foner, 2015; Crul et al., 2014, 2012; García-Carmona et al., 2020). As this literature suggests, the crossing of national borders necessitates a gradual process of intercultural education in the resocialization of immigrant children and of their parents. As critical contexts of reception, schools, families, and communities are central in this dynamic process. Without systemic interventions and social justice leadership practices these youths often face exclusion and a greater risk of becoming a public burden.

In the last decades, technological advances have led school principals to modernize their pedagogical approaches while challenged by limited resources. Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) can be used as a strategy for inclusion, avoiding a new type of social inequality

between those who have access to and knowledge of the technology and those who do not (James, 2001). This is most acute in school systems within cities or regions sharing contiguous borders, often divided by geopolitical laws, culture, and inversely disproportioned economies, as the case of Morocco and Spain illustrates. School leaders within immigrant contexts of reception face challenges accommodating the needs of children and those of families importing none or limited human capital resources (Crul et al., 2012). However, we argue that within immigrant contexts of reception, educational leaders may be the first to accumulate experiential knowledge about the school needs of immigrant youth. These leaders may be also first to propose pedagogical models of inclusion framed within social justice perspectives, aimed at increasing the integration of youth socialized between two nations and cultures.

The autonomous City of Melilla presents an ideal case for understanding how leaders within multicultural contexts and minority-majority schools implement social justice education. As a traditional European immigrant point of entry within Northern Africa, Melilla's nationhood history has been shaped by the enforcement of borders and immigration, but also the preemptive foresight of educational leaders in accommodating Iberian and Moorish cultures in their pedagogical approaches. However, unprecedented waves of immigrants from Africa and Asia, seeking refuge status in Spain and other nations within the Mediterranean basin, have increased the concentration of foreign-born, disadvantaged youth in Melilla's schools (MECD, 2017). Paradoxically, among all OECD nations, Spain and Portugal experience the highest index of school attrition but also of students who enter higher education (Roth & Thum, 2010). Yet, we lack insights as to how students in minority-majority schools fare (Carter, 2010). An interesting paradox we further examine is how school leaders in multicultural contexts of reception, like Melilla, may be at the vanguard of social justice pedagogies, as well as the design of intercultural practices that are more democratic and inclusive.

Since the 1980s, Intercultural Education (IE) has been the major platform for dialogs about diversity and democracy. Intercultural education has been adopted by the United Nations, UNESCO and the Council of Europe as the basis for interreligious and interfaith initiatives and the internationalization of schools. As it is, in many OECD nations, IE is the dominant paradigm for cultural policy, the development of teaching practices and curriculum designs. It is postulated as an inclusive model for reducing xenophobia and racism. However, politicians and educators blame poor education outcomes on failed multiculturalism and link immigrants and minorities for the failure of poorly managed schools. Other times, school leaders, mostly principals, are targeted for failing to implement structural or cultural solutions to reduce historical inequalities among the disadvantaged (Burrello et al., 2001; Dantley & Tillman, 2006). We argue in this paper that these debates overlook the cultural resources of immigrant reception schools and the unique role of school leaders in the design of intercultural pedagogical approaches.

The main premise of our paper is that leadership for social justice is a form of activism that seeks to transform educational environments into spaces where students and educators can thrive, even when, apparently, the odds do not always seem favorable. This qualitative study seeks to explore the social justice ideologies and practices of leaders in culturally diverse schools of Melilla (Spain). Guided by immigration, educational leadership, and social justice frameworks, the research questions driving this paper are, what ideologies drive the social justice practices of school leaders in majority-minority school contexts like Melilla? How can culturally relevant or intercultural education be implemented as a form of social justice? What is the role of ICT in this form of education? And, what challenges do leaders experience in highly diverse, minority-majority schools? Below, we explain the three main frameworks guiding our study on the leadership and social justice ideologies and practices of principals within highly diverse, minority-majority schools: Leadership for Social Justice, Culturally Relevant Leadership/Intercultural Education, and ICT as a form of Applied Social Justice Education and Leadership in Multicultural Contexts.

Leadership for social justice

There is an extant literature on social justice and leadership. However, not perspectives address moralistic approaches, based on “respect, equity, and equal opportunities for all individuals, regardless of race, ethnicity, creed, (dis)ability, gender, class, economic status, and other marginalizing conditions” (King & Travers, 2017, p. 148). A limitation of this scholarship is that its application is context-specific, and may be differently understood by different disciplines and fields (Bogotch, 2015; Robinson, 2017). Its meaning may also convey different approaches in diverse societies or social contexts (Bogotch, 2002; Leithwood & Riehl, 2005; Taysum & Gunter, 2008). More significantly, the universal right to an education in the US may be different in China, Europe, or Latin America. Cultural variations may also influence how students are treated in the educational system or the classroom.

Overall, by now scholars concede that social justice leadership in schools must be dynamic, open to social change, and responsive to “time, place, and political context” (Hajisoteriou & Angelides, 2014, p. 897). All social justice/educational reform efforts, therefore, must be deliberately and continuously reinvented and critiqued (Bogotch, 2002). Social justice leadership fights against the status quo as leaders are aware mainstream education marginalizes large numbers of students and their families, preventing them from being heard or even acknowledged (Shields, 2014). In this process social justice leaders are often challenged moving from ideology to the practice of a more equitable public school environment (Theoharis, 2007), especially as they take an increasingly imminent role in the implementation of social justice practices (Angelle, 2017; Blackmore, 2006; King & Travers, 2017; Miller et al., 2019). We extend this literature by examining the social justice ideologies and practices of leaders in culturally diverse, minority-majority schools, where leaders face unique challenges despite their first-hand experiences working with diverse student populations (Arar et al., 2019; Miller et al., 2019; Ylimaki et al., 2007).

In the last decade, researchers have addressed how class, race, and even gender differences affect the design and implementation of pedagogical social justice practices. This scholarship demonstrates that teachers’ expectations of students differ as many tend to favor those who share their middle-class values (Lareau, 2002; Portes & Rumbaut, 2001, 2005). This scholarship also reveals that parents with low human and social capital are often disadvantaged in schools. Immigrant parents often do not understand the host educational system or what their children’s schools expect of them (Crul et al., 2014, 2012; García-Carmona et al., 2020; Fuentes-Mayorga, 2012).

Leadership for social justice, therefore, advocates for a new form of activism in both its intent and approach, one which includes culturally relative and context-specific education, as the next survey of the literature illustrates. This study is, as far as we know, the first to pioneer a social justice leadership approach in Melilla’s schools. The way it is perceived is based on principles of equity and fairness among the different communities and cultures that coexist in the city and therefore in the schools. This approach takes into account the use of social justice leadership, culturally relevant/Intercultural Education, and ICT, as parallel processes of social inclusion.

Intercultural education and culturally relevant leadership

Since the early 1990s, scholars have studied the role of intercultural and multicultural education as a form of inclusion. We distinguish between the two approaches as they are related but at once distinct. For example, while *multicultural education* has been linked to pluralism and the factual coexistence of people of diverse cultures (Camilleri, 1992), *intercultural education* suggests interaction among groups who share respect and understanding of separate cultures, where preconceived biases as obstacles to communication are removed. As a main tool of social justice, intercultural education (IE) has been postulated to raise the standards of our present educational system (Banks, 1993). However, as the IE movement is still in its infancy, scholars need guidance on the types of schools and populations which can most benefit from its implementation. But, where should we look for effective IE or culturally relevant educational models?

Studies comparing the educational integration of immigrants youth in the United States and Spain, mostly those of ethno-racial minorities with colonial ties in Latin America and North Africa (Alba & Holdaway, 2013; Gibson & Carrasco, 2009; OECD, 2010, 2012; Telles & Ortiz, 2008) demonstrate the key role of school resources and that of culturally-relevant education in reducing legacies of school inequality in minority-majority, reception schools. The Civil Rights Act (1964; Cited in Banks 1996) in the United States and the European Maastricht Treaty (1993; Cited in Rego and Nieto 2000), albeit separated by three decades, have outlined educational standards and social justice reforms for the inclusion of minority students. These acts forbade discrimination on account of race, color, creed, or national origin in any federally funded activity and have led to the development of other movements for inclusive social justice education. For example, in the US, in the early 1980s, the enactment of multicultural educational laws culminated in the development of bilingual education within public schools, mostly to address the educational gaps of language minority, immigrant youth. However, bilingual education has been associated mostly with racialized ethnic minorities, especially with poor, Hispanic youth. Intercultural and dual-language education, on the contrary, has been associated and made mostly available to mainstream, native-born, middle-class families (Gundara & Sharma, 2010; OECD, 2010, 2012; Fuentes-Mayorga, 2012).

It is, therefore, a leaders' responsibility to address these issues and advocate on behalf of students, teachers, and community members whose educational experience is negatively affected by these socio-political forces (Normore & Brooks, 2014). Culturally Relevant Leadership (CRL) may be the best approach to influence the school context and address the cultural needs of the entire educational community, to develop, along with these actors, a critical consciousness, identifying and challenging inequities inherent in the larger society (Arar et al., 2019; López, 2016). Scholars (Horsford et al., 2011) have identified four components where CRL must be implemented; namely in the political contexts (demographic divide, competing values, ideologies, and perspectives); in pedagogical approaches (culturally relevant and antiracist approaches); in personal journeys (cultural proficiency) and as part of a professional duty (leading for equity, engagement, and excellence). As the work of leadership scholars Khalifa et al. (2016) reveals, CRL must work to include their staff to "support and promote a climate that makes the whole school welcoming, inclusive, and accepting of minoritized students" (p. 1275). This approach is found to increase leadership for social justice within immigrant schools contexts and develop practical student-centered frameworks (Brooks et al., 2017).

Overall this literature suggests that CRL and responsive leadership models emerge only when administrators function as public intellectuals, curriculum innovators, and social activists (Gooden & O'Doherty, 2015; Johnson, 2006). Scholars conclude that in immigrant reception schools "challenges are multifaceted, related policy still develops and culturally relevant leadership and multicultural practices are necessary for integration" (Arar et al., 2020, p. 18). We extend these insights with an exploration of the social justice leadership ideologies and practices of principals in minority-majority schools within Melilla, Spain, and the mechanisms that facilitate and deter their application.

Applied social justice education and leadership in multicultural contexts

To explore the social justice efforts of school leaders with applied culturally relevant education, the study by Santamaría et al. (2014) is illustrative. Drawing on critical race and gendered approaches, the authors examine how the ethnic, racial, and gendered identity of two Mexican-descent school leaders within a lower (K-6) and a higher (university) educational setting in the United States affect educational practices in multicultural contexts. The results suggest that minority leaders' identities and their use of culturally relevant pedagogical approaches, drawing on their own experiences and identities, resulted in effective, equitable leadership outcomes that increased the educational participation and empowerment of students.

Although Spain lags behind in the study of applied, social justice leadership, an emerging scholarship has addressed school leadership and social justice within minority-majority schools. For example, a study in Huelva, a city in southern Spain, with a large school concentration of Muslim/Berber

students (Gómez-Hurtado, 2014) explores the social justice practices of educational leaders and managers within a few centers of early childhood and primary education. The findings suggest the need for further research within, multicultural contexts which are focused on a commitment to an open education community, and a collaborative culture of partnership between leaders, educators, and management teams. Despite the author's timely and cogent contributions, the ethnic, racial, or gender identities of leaders in this study were not included.

Whereas a number of studies document the importance of social change in the leadership of schools in Spain (Murillo, 2006; García-Carmona, 2014), only a few studies address the identity of school leaders within multicultural contexts of education (Murillo & Hernández-Castilla, 2011; García-Carmona, 2014). Even when studies show that leadership is affected by shifts in population and multicultural diversity (Ainscow & West, 2008; Lumby & Coleman, 2010), we still lack a good understanding of how the identity of minority leaders, such as those of women or people of color affects their leadership practices (Arar et al., 2019; Méndez-Morse, 2000). In the early 1980s, studies advocating transformational leadership practices omitted the identity of leaders (Bass, 1981). However, since the first decade of the millennium, researchers have explored how race and gender affect leadership practices. A scholarship on social justice leadership advocating the inclusion of leaders who will promote equitable educational leadership, the closing of educational gaps and other of inequities in schools is today a top priority (Shapiro & Stefkovich, 2016).

The search for models of social justice leadership increasingly includes those employed within multicultural educational contexts. While Santamaría and collaborators seek the inclusion of culturally relevant education in school contexts with legacies of institutional exclusion, others, (White et al., 2014) examine the empowerment of students within contexts affected by colonization, such as Latin America. Through the use of critical pedagogy and culturally relevant education, these authors show how Central American leaders struggle to educate minority youth to compete in their new, globalized, neo-liberal economies. Yet, these authors question how can students compete in national contexts that continue to experience colonial forms of domination and power struggles through their economies? Their findings contribute critical knowledge on the inherent contradictions of social justice pedagogies that aim to increase minority students' access to education in contexts and cultures still impregnated by colonial domination.

Research among school leaders in remote, rural, schools of England, Jamaica, and Spain (Miller et al., 2019) reveals that the unique structures of these smaller, remote schools, increase the chances of effective social justice pedagogy. The limited size of the schools populations allows the greater reach and establishment of closer relationships with families, as well as the design of activities adapted to varied needs of students. We explore how school leaders establish programs to integrate students, including the hard-to-reach, vulnerable students, and their families. We further explore what has helped these leaders to include social justice education and the application of curriculums as social justice tools to address the needs of all school members. We analyze too the role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in mediating this process.

Information communication technologies and social justice

Advances in the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) sector have made it easier for more people to have access to education and reduce digital gaps (Willems, 2019). In addition, they have enhanced educational efforts to promote social justice. As mentioned by Vrasidas et al. (2009, p. 7) "poverty, social inclusion and cultural understanding can be addressed via a variety of ICTs including mobile technologies, Web 2.0 tools, online games, social networking software, and networked learning environments". In this way, ICT may facilitate the increased integration and interaction of millions of people around the world into activities, independence in space and time, and unlimited opportunities for collaboration.

Research shows that ICT increases the inclusion and participation of students and access to a more flexible and open teaching and learning environment. The digitalization of classrooms also allows the use of different platforms of instruction; increase of interactive exchanges and participation of teachers, and hard-to-reach students and

families (García-Carmona et al., 2020). This emerging literature also shows that parents and teachers associations in schools benefit from the Internet to communicate with vulnerable, “hard-to-reach”, immigrant families. PA/PTAs leaders have a key role as channels of communication between schools and families but also in the mode in which this communication increases the participation of families from diverse social origins. These leadership and technological tools mediate the narrowing of cultural and class differences in the classroom.

As mentioned above, the use of ICT promotes access to education, especially among the “hard-to-reach”, and the underprivileged, through online education programs, designed to reach out communities and individuals who, otherwise, could not attend traditional schools (Vrasidas et al., 2009; Willems, 2019). Also, these authors find ICT builds learning environments within which individuals and communities can learn and also take action to promote social justice, intercultural education, reconciliation, and social inclusion. We extend these insights with an exploration of the use of ICT as a tool for promoting social justice leadership within the educational community in minority-majority schools in Melilla, and the strategies that facilitate or impede their use.

Methodology

Research design and participants

This descriptive case study (Miles & Huberman, 1994) presents the views of Melilla’s principals, our unit of analysis. We explore social justice ideologies and practices of social justice of school leaders in Melilla. As is characteristic of qualitative research designs, the sample selection for the participants uses a purposive sampling method (Tójar, 2006). The sampling selection process ended when we reached a theoretical saturation point, when additional interviews no longer provided additional information relevant to our questions (Glaser & Strauss, 1967).

The City of Melilla has six elementary (K-12) school districts, with two school principals per district. Our study includes one school principal from each district. We have selected six leaders in order to achieve representation for each district. We include three female and three male leaders, to also promote gender representation. The aggregate, combined teaching experience of head school teachers is 199 years; and of school principals is 114 years. The leadership experiences of these six principals are organized as high, average, and low (see Table 1).

A keystone distinction of Melilla’s schools is its cultural diversity. All six schools participating in the study have a minority-majority student populations, ranging from 60% to 90% of students with Berber origin and *Tamazight* language. Particularly interesting is the case of the school in District 6, where the student body is 98% Muslim/Berber and the teachers’ years of experience is also the highest. Also, District 6 concentrates the highest share of students, 947 compared with the average of two other districts (D1 and D2) of six, hovering on the low 300s. An interesting point is the higher ratio (34) of teacher-students in District 2, compared to the average in most other schools (28). School principals were assigned pseudonyms “P” and the number of the District (for example; P1 representing principal in District 1), as illustrated in Table 1, below.

The context of Melilla

This study takes place in the Autonomous City of Melilla, Spain. The City is delimited by the northern region of Morocco, known as the Riff in North Africa. It encompasses a territory of about 12 Km² with a population of approximately 86,120 inhabitants (INE, 2017). Melilla counts with a very dense population, above the medium for Spain and the European Union (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2019). The City is particularly interesting for a study of school leadership for social justice because of its history of immigration and long legacy accommodating immigrant students. Melilla’s inhabitants have origins in North Africa and in Spain but also from other nations in the Mediterranean Basin. Within this small City, Christians and Muslims compose the two largest religious groups (each above 50%). The Muslim population is Berber and its maternal language is *tamazight*, a derivative of *Tarifit*, the Berber language of the

Table 1. Sample of public school leaders and districts demographics in Melilla, Spain (K-12).

Items/Participants	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
*Students' Ethno-Religious Identity	90% Muslim (Berber) 9% Christian 1% Gypsy	70% Muslim (Berber) 29% Christian 1% Gypsy	90% Muslim (Berber) 10% Christian	60% Muslim 39% Christian 1% Gypsy	90% Muslim (Berber) 9% Christian 1% Gypsy	98% Muslim (Berber) 10% Christian 1% Gypsy
*Principals' Ethno-Religious Identity	Christian	Christian	Christian	Christian	Christian	Christian
School District	1	2	3	4	5	6
Teaching experience (years)	26	41	28	19	40	45
Leadership experience (years)	11	24	14	4	31	30
Leadership experience (years) in how many (K-12) schools	2	3	1	1	2	2
Gender of Leader	F	M	F	F	M	M
Ratio	20	34	30	30	29	25
Student enrolled at current school	215	285	816	877	520	947

*Defined by the Instituto de las Culturas de Melilla (2019).

original settlers in this region. Melilla has the highest concentration of immigrant youth in public schools (K-12) than any other schools in Spain, with Moroccan youth making up the largest majority. Other cultures and religious groups (Judaic-Hebrew, Hindu, and Gipsie) make up smaller shares (2%) but also contribute to Melilla's distinctive multicultural diversity (Instituto de las Culturas de Melilla, 2019). Lastly, the City's student/teacher ratio is the highest compared to other regions or Spain (Marmolejo & Montero-Alonso, 2009, p. 154).

Within Melilla's multicultural context there is a movement toward intercultural assimilation. For example, the adoption of intercultural education in schools aims at enhancing the knowledge and respect of diverse cultures and, in turn, the mutual enrichment and collective efforts toward the creation of a larger, intercultural society, based on mutual respect (Aguado et al., 2014; García-Carmona, 2014, 2015; García-Carmona et al., 2020). Such cultural diversity "facilitates a learning environment around social multiculturality" (Vilà, 2006, p. 356). Our study further explores how social justice leadership and pedagogy affect these practices.

Finally, we want to stress that Melilla does not have an institution in which its local political system is organized. The Spanish State, through the Ministry of Education and Professional Capacitation in its central capital of Madrid, is the sole entity responsible for regulating and managing Melilla's educational system (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2019).

Interviews and procedure

To identify and evaluate the ideologies and practices of school leaders in Melilla's culturally diverse, minority-majority schools, we use a qualitative approach. We conduct in-depth, semi-structured, face-to-face interviews with six school principals. We obtained informed consent from all participants prior to the formal interview. Each interview lasted between 45 and 60 minute and were conducted in an informal, conversational style that encouraged participants' open discussions about their role as school leaders, their ideologies and strategies around social justice education. All personal information was deleted, and each transcript assigned a code to guaranteed anonymity. All interviews were recorded and professionally transcribed. To gain access to schools we asked the permission of the Faculty of Educational Sciences and Sports at the University of Granada, Spain, and from the Consejería de Educación de la Ciudad Autónoma de Melilla (Council of Education in Melilla).

Data analysis

To analyze the interviews' insights, we used a content analysis method (Bardin, 1996; Miles & Huberman, 1994). This method includes phases of categorization, text distribution, and content analysis. The first step involved identifying the different categories that emerged from the meta-category (the overarching category), "the ideologies and practices of school leaders in order to enhance social justice within culturally diverse, minority-majority schools. We have identified six sub-categories to address our research questions: 1) Social justice from the views of school leaders in minority-majority schools, 2) Leadership for social justice practices; 3) Intercultural Education and Social Justice; 4) ICT as tools for modernization and inclusivity; 5) Social Justice Leadership and Curriculum; and 6) Symbolic Social Justice Leadership. The second step of our analysis is organized by the following question: what triggers school leaders within multicultural contexts to implement social justice practices? This step involved scrutinizing the text passages within each category. The third step complemented the analysis of linking the categories with the objective of addressing the general question framing this study. It involved going back and forth between the original transcript passages and the original question. This ensured that no relevant aspect was omitted through paraphrasing and summarizing of the interviewees' narratives.

The following matrix connects the different categories of analysis with our research questions and helps better understand how the findings will be presented (Table 2):

Table 2. Relation between the research questions and the categories of analysis.

Research question	Categories of analysis
1) What ideologies drive the social justice practices of school leaders in majority-minority school contexts like Melilla?	Social justice from the views of school leaders in minority-majority schools Leadership for social justice practices
2) How is intercultural education implemented as a form of social justice?	Intercultural Education and Social Justice
3) What is the role of ICT in this form of education?	ICT as tools for modernization and inclusivity
4) What challenges do leaders experience in highly diverse, minority-majority schools?	Social Justice Leadership and Curriculum Symbolic Social Justice Leadership

Positionality

Each one of the authors has a long history of work in education. The lead author has extensive experience working as a teacher in elementary schools in the City of Granada (Spain) and also in higher education in the City of Melilla. The third author also has worked in higher education in the City of Melilla. The second author has over fifteen years of experience in higher education within private and public institutions. She currently works in the flagship college of the City University of New York, a public college and institution with a minority-majority student body composed mostly of children of immigrants from Latin America, Asia, and Africa. Both the first and third authors are of Iberian descent, born and socialized in Granada; the third author is of Afro-Caribbean and Iberian descent, an immigrant adolescent socialized, and educated in DR and New York City. All three authors are bilingual (Spanish and English) and socialized or educated within multicultural and transnational immigrant settings. As educators, all three authors take into consideration the gender, race, ethnic, and class differences separating or uniting them with their students. They also practice social justice pedagogies through culturally relevant education and ICT. These practices often entail for the second author, the sharing of her own experiences of exclusion and also of empowerment and mobility in the educational system of the U.S. educational system; and for the first and third author, they entail recognizing their positions as native-born members of the ruling majority in minority-majority- majority schools settings of Melilla, as well as their dedication to improving the inclusivity of disadvantaged youth. These practices, the authors find, increase their students' self-esteem and sense of pride as well as respect for their education in culturally diverse context of education.

Findings

The purpose of this study is to identify and evaluate the ideologies and practices of school leaders toward the enhancement of social justice education within the culturally diverse, minority-majority school context of Melilla. Six main themes around social justice and leadership emerged from our interviews with school principals.

Social justice from the views of school leaders in minority-majority schools

Leaders in our study identified social justice framed within a larger, ethical, or moralistic perspective. Their ideologies often emphasizing such universal values as “equity” and “equality” for all, substantiating the findings of previous scholars, as noted in our survey of the literature. Leaders' ideologies about social justice often addressed the importance of fairness and equality, or of giving every student what is just and necessary for their wellbeing and development, as the case in Melilla public school system illustrates. Unanimously, leaders felt that social justice should be inclusive, not only relevant within the school setting but also in the immediate school community, and the larger society. This is emphasized most strongly by a school principal in district 4, below:

We need to give everyone the opportunity and the resources they need; so that everyone has equal access in society. Even when we start from different socioeconomic positions, and family structures, as it is in many cases, this will balance inequality, allowing all citizens to have an equal chance at personal development (P4, District 4).

A similar moralistic-driven ideology is shared by P3. This time with an emphasis on the need of the larger Spanish society to practice social justice as a moral right, one which must target the inclusion of disadvantaged citizens in education. The emotive yet critical views of this leader are illustrated below:

We need to strive for an equal distribution of resources in society. In a society where social justice is the norm, there is much more respect for human rights and for the inclusion and assistance of disadvantaged groups in reaching their potential development. Yet, it is difficult to reach this type of social justice because we [as humans] are very selfish; however, it is a fact that we can always help the most disadvantaged through social public aid intervention. This does not have to be imposed; it should be a natural process. (P3, District 3).

We observe that both P3 and P4 are female leaders. Both have the least years of teaching experience working in K-12 public school grades. However, unlike Leader in P4, P3's school concentrates one of the highest shares of Muslim/Berber students. This leader feels that social justice should be mostly based on moral principles, but also an innate part of the educational curriculum, "it is difficult to reach this type of social justice because we [as humans] are selfish. This does not have to be imposed; it should be a natural process."

When asked if social justice was key to their school leadership, again, most leaders emphasized that social justice is a very relevant concept for their leadership and pedagogical practices. They all felt social justice practices create conditions that increase equality and opportunities for the entire school community of Melilla. They emphasize the need to increase the autonomy and empowerment of leaders, as well as those of students, teachers, families, and the supporting staff as forms of social justice and in ensuring these students' access to mainstream education. However, these ideologies do not often include radical transformation of the curriculum or of the structure or authority that oversees them or their school districts. Similarly, P2's and P5's schools exhibit the highest concentration of minority students and the highest years of teaching and leadership experience, only, next to P6. This may explain leaders' strong conviction that social justice practices must include the input of the larger community, or those of students, teachers, families, and the larger Spanish society. Most important, these leaders are also the most critical of the system's failure to integrate minority students as well as parents, as P2 further substantiates:

I understand that public entities must meet the needs and services of disadvantaged families. I realize this is not what is being done [in Melilla]. The equal rights decree of our constitution is not being met. I also think that schooling for parents is very important. When these programs are open to parents within the educational system or in school settings people notice the difference. This is the educational agenda should be that one: a coordination of efforts between schools and parents. But, we know that there are families that do not have their eyes on their students (P2, District 2).

It is really important to understand what social justice entails. If you don't understand it, nothing can be done within our schools. Nothing can be done to improve the conditions of students, and also those among teachers, and those of people who work in maintenance or who clean our schools; including our supporting staff and families (P5, District 5).

These views depict Melilla's school leaders' reflections about the limited power dynamics they hold within their local school district, and the failure of their centralized system to meet the educational needs of minority students. Some leaders also blame parents for their students' delimited school outcomes. The findings extend a scholarship on critical leadership as a form of social justice in the integration of vulnerable student populations in contexts shaped by a history of immigration (Arar et al., 2020).

Leadership for social justice practices

Most school leaders in this study strongly voiced that social justice must be an inherent part of their leadership. Yet, when it comes to praxis, or implementation of social justice in schools, they see as priority to improve the conditions of their educational communities, reaffirming always the key role of

teachers and of the family. To carry on these initiatives, these leaders depend on the political and financial support of local and federal entities to increase equality among youth with economic or academic disadvantages, through the aid of scholarships. However, since they face limited allocation from their Ministry of Education, these leaders must constantly seek help from other local and international organizations, as a leader (P3) in District 3 emphasizes:

The City of Melilla and the Education Ministry provide economic assistance through scholarships. “Cáritas” provides financial assistance for disadvantaged youth and their families in our community. Also Melilla Acoge gives service in schools for mothers, where many [immigrants and language minorities] learn Spanish and also can do physical exercises (P3, District 3).

Beyond emphasizing the key role of financial resources, leaders blame the central educational system’s limited understanding of the needs of students in Melilla’s schools as well as those of their leaders. As [Table 1](#) and our qualitative findings reveal, Melilla school districts concentrate the highest shares of students of North African ancestry than other cities in Spain (Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional, 2019). As the leader of school District 1 further stresses below, schools in Melilla face limited authority to implement social justice programs of inclusion, “they should allow more autonomy in our schools! More liberty!”

Another leader in District 6, which concentrates the largest majority (96%) of Moroccan Berber students, voices similar frustrations about the lack of financial assistance and autonomy of Melilla’s schools leaders even in these leaders’ ability to accommodate students with special needs:

The financial assistance we receive is not sufficient; leaving us with many unmet necessities, as for example, infrastructural limitations in our facilities to accommodate access to handicapped students! (P6, District 6).

District 6 is an interesting case. Besides concentrating the majority of ethno-religious student minorities; the school has one of the lowest teacher-student ratios, and the highest cumulative experience among K-12 teachers. This leader is among one of the first to explain how their social justice leadership practices are truncated by a multiplicity of limitations; but, mostly because leaders in Melilla’s school districts have only “symbolic leadership” power, unable to exert autonomy or influence changes in the school curriculum which often do not meet the needs of their minority students. These findings extend an emerging scholarship documenting the strong link between ineffective policies and the systemic, exclusion of ethno-racial student minorities in schools (Telles & Ortiz, 2008). The findings also corroborate an international scholarship which has captured the thwarted educational experiences of refugee Syrian students (Arar et al., 2020) due primordially to bureaucratic and political limitations.

ICT as tools for modernization and inclusivity

Our qualitative insights further reveal that all school leaders in Melilla recognize the importance of ICT to enhance their pedagogical and social justice practices. Teachers play a key role not only in capacitating students’ digital literacy, including integrating hard-to-reach students and parents, but also in protecting them from the harm of virtual environments. Most important, ICT increases equality in the access to education, building of community and its member’s participation as well as in critical pedagogy, as more explicitly shared by leaders in district 2 and 6:

It is important to take advantage of the potential advantages of technology as another window or door into the world. Besides, it is important to acknowledge and take advantage of its availability and potential for distraction. However, it is necessary to educate children to become intelligent and critical users, so that they know about the speed at which ICT information spreads; how to discern what is true and what is fake or damaging information. Towards this end, teachers have a key role to play. (P2, District 2).

The use of ICT allows us to work with all the different aspects of the teaching curriculum, and emphasize and share ideas about equality, the equal right to resources and to a quality education to all students (P6, District 6).

As the above narratives attest, most school leaders use ICT to promote social justice as a form of inclusion and giving equal access to all students, especially those who are “hard-to-reach” and their families.

Children must have access to devices in our schools because in their homes many don't have a computer. The Internet and technology opens your mind to a world of possibilities and of infinite information. Indeed, Information & Communication Technologies are very important, and so is their use, as long as the use is sensible (P3, District 3).

Despite the growing significance of ICT in society, economic resources are scarce. There are too many students who lack computers or access to the Internet at home. We have a web page but have realized very few parents ever look at it. Some of our teachers also have their own applications to communicate with their students' parents, but, again, few of them look at them! (P5, District 5).

Yet, as P3 and P4 emphasized above, limited access to resources prevents many school leaders from acquiring needed ICT infrastructure and technological support. These limitations introduce additional forms of inequality affecting mostly disadvantaged students. However, despite leaders' efforts to increase the digital literacy of students and of families, some leaders report frustration as many families cannot afford to buy computers or lack education about ICT. These limitations may explain the low responsiveness of parents in minority-majority schools. Our findings also suggest these leaders view ICT as a tool for increasing the reach of disadvantaged students and participation of parents and the educational community (Morato et al., 2020). The inclusion of these students will increase the quality and access of education among disadvantaged and hard to reach minorities, as well as contribute to reducing digital inequality gaps in schools (Campos-Soto et al., 2018).

Intercultural education and social justice

Beyond the use of ICT tools, leaders conceptualized intercultural education as part of social justice activities, designed to promote the equal exchange and respect of cultural diversity within the school environment and the larger community. Many of these intercultural activities are part of the Educational Project of each school. Intercultural education ideologies are similarly framed within moralistic perspectives and are mainly targeted at students' embracing and sharing of cultural values of minority and majority groups, based on mutual respect, equality, peace, co-education, inclusion and diversity, including civil engagement. This form of applied social justice education is stressed, as the leader of district 5 and 6 emphasizes, below:

We treat everyone equally here. There are complementary activities such as the day of peace, or women's day . . . We also work on values on a daily basis in an interdisciplinary way. We are also very much committed to coeducation and democratization between the sexes. Even though the Christian student is a minority, we celebrate the feasts of the different cultures, the customs, the food . . . (P5, District 5).

Here, we celebrate all cultures putting aside religious themes aside. The festive themes are cultural. We use these opportunities to work on other themes such as consumerism; recycling, and even solidarity We strive to develop competency and a shared value about equality, visibility, social justice (P6, District 6).

Our finding reveals that schools can benefit from the cultural resources, strengths, and contributions of culturally diverse students populations. We also find that the whole educational community benefits from improved communication systems and practices that focus on intercultural exchanges. These inclusive practices allow the entire school to become enriched and better prepared to offer new and more democratic forms of learning that are representative of diverse cultures and can produce future, cultural savvy, global citizens, as the recent work of educational leadership and migration scholars (García-Carmona et al., 2020) reveals.

Social justice leadership and curriculum

Finally, school leaders vehemently emphasized that a uniform way of applied social justice is through the adoption of a singular educational curriculum. One that will make all students feel included. However, most leaders felt the content of this curriculum must be relevant to the diversity of cultures, these different cultural groups' histories; as well as their inclusive methodologies and common goals. Yet, to achieve these objectives, the different political powers must arrive at a consensus about the laws of education:

The laws that reform education should be agreed upon by the different political forces in order to reach a consensus. In my opinion, health and education are fundamental aspects for society. Obviously it will not be for life, because nothing is perfect, but it can be updated and revised over time to suit new needs (P2, District 2).

I think what we are missing is the tutoring session as it happens in high schools. Perhaps establishing at least one hour a week . . . one could work on those social and civic values (P4, District 4).

School leaders unanimously agreed that social justice principles must be reflected in the school curriculum. As the leader in P4 emphasizes above, the new curriculum should include more academic support for disadvantaged students, such as tutoring. Yet these principles are merely placed as ideologies or intended objectives. The limited access to financial and personnel support, restrict these leaders' abilities to make concrete revisions to the curriculum. This is exacerbated by the lack of a multidisciplinary team to give the school the support needed. They also feel these changes must come from the top and implemented "vertically," as explained by a leader in District 2:

We talk about children with specific educational support needs, learning difficulties . . . but then we do not offer the multidisciplinary team that the schools need to meet all the needs. The changes should be implemented vertically, that is, first from the educational administration and followed by the teachers and other members of the educational community. The teacher is the one who must guide the process, so the more he or she is helped and the more resources and tools he or she has, the more effective the work will be". (P2, District 2).

These views reflect the importance of leaders' capacities to make substantive and meaningful change. Social justice content needs to be explicitly included in the curriculum and in the teachers' training/education programs (Miller et al., 2019). However, we find that minority-majority schools represent a challenge not so much to the practice of intercultural exchanges, but to the limited financial resources of schools and leaders' limited political bargaining power. They also experience bureaucratic barriers (Arar et al., 2020), which restrict the access to resources and, in turn, the integration of students. This brings us to one last and central finding about the challenges faced by leaders within minority-majority, and immigrant reception, schools.

Symbolic social justice leadership

The previous analysis of findings mainly illustrates that leaders' ideologies and practices of intercultural education are limited, as the implementation of social justice requires the transformation of the school curriculum. School leaders unanimously stressed how these transformational changes must be integrated from the top down, or directly from the educational leadership and [then] replicated by teachers and members of the larger educational community. Table 1, for example, illustrates that Muslim/Berber culture predominates in all of the six school districts in Melilla, why conceptualize them as "minority-majority" learning centers. Interestingly, we find that most of these schools concentrate leaders with the greatest longevity or years of teaching (K-12) experience. Yet, despite these leaders' highly qualified capacitation, their social justice practices are thwarted as their teaching curriculum does not represent the needs of their rapidly changing student population. A culprit is their lack of autonomy or bargaining power with their central system of education, as P5 and P2 emphasize, below:

Now there is a lot of talk about the autonomy of the centers, but it is a fallacy. They tell us what to do and we can't get out of it. We are given a curriculum that does not interest the children. There are more important issues and themes such as social justice or the environment. There is little freedom and time is thrown at us and, of course, they demand results. (P5, District 5).

Each educational institution, depending on its school population, needs and shortages, should have a little more freedom in choosing its curriculum. Teachers should have more autonomy to place greater emphasis on the development of certain instrumental skills (study techniques, reading, mathematics . . .) in function of the needs that are observed in the classroom (P2, District 2).

Each school should be allowed to work on certain issues that are a priority according to the context, depending on the profile of the students. (P4, District 4).

As these leaders and most others emphasize, a lack of authority limits their input in making the curriculum more culturally relevant to the education of youth in highly diverse school contexts. Yet, even when social justice objectives are included in the annual planning meetings of the curriculum, these are mostly focused on working groups in the classroom and the inclusion of cultural and civic activities, as illustrated below:

Fundamentally through the annual classroom programming, we work on contents and activities from different cultures, in the same way and giving the same importance to each of them, as well as values such as tolerance, respect . . . which are fundamental for coexistence. (P1, District 1).

We work as a team. We discuss it among the management team and we are also in contact with the pedagogical committee. We meet to see what the needs and priorities are. (P5, District 5).

Discussion, conclusion and recommendations

The purpose of this study was to identify and evaluate the social justice ideologies and practices of school leaders within multicultural contexts, using the case study of Melilla, Spain. Analysis of educational reports as well as the interviews insights reveal that most of Melilla's schools concentrate a majority student population, composed mostly of ethno-religious, Muslim minorities (Moroccan/Berber). The school leadership is homogeneously composed by a Christian minority (Spaniards). Although majority in numbers, Muslims families with limited resources face intersectional racial, class, and cultural inequality. Often students and families lack familiarity with the mainstream Spanish culture as well as its educational system, despite a Spanish citizenship. In contexts with a long history of immigration, as is the case of Melilla, we argue, schools play a key and yet unique role in the education as well as cultural socialization of ethno-racial, and class-based, student minorities.

Our examination of social justice leadership ideologies reveals that leaders' ideologies ranged from a focus on students' education and integration through intercultural education and ICT as well as the internalization of democratic principles about peace, collaboration, and equality. Social justice ideologies, however, also address the transformation of the educational curriculum. Leaders unanimously agree that this initiative requires the collaboration of the larger school community (Wade et al., 2019), and the input of teachers and those of "hard-to-reach" families (García-Carmona et al., 2020), as research reveals. Leaders view most favorably social justice initiatives to benefit all students and decrease the school failures of disadvantaged youths. These objectives require the input of all leaders, and the larger community to work inclusivity, independent of their national, racial, or socioeconomic origin (Sarid, 2019).

Analysis of Melilla's models of school leadership suggests social justice pedagogy in these schools is practiced through Culturally Relevant Leadership, in this case, Intercultural Education, targeted at the equal exchange of cultural values between Muslims and Christians as well as other religious and non-religious minorities as a form of civic engagement as well as promotion of a school environment that is welcoming and inclusive, supporting the observations of earlier scholars (Khalifa et al., 2016). However, in culturally diverse schools (Arar et al., 2020), leadership practice requires clear, supportive,

and facilitating policy guidelines as well as awareness of social justice leadership for healthy integration. To this end, leaders in Melilla schools view ICT as a tool to increase social justice through the inclusion of disadvantaged students and parents (Morato et al., 2020). School leaders note that these practices have increased the quality and access of education as well as reduces digital inequality gaps, substantiating the previous findings of ICT and educational scholars (Campos-Soto et al., 2018). However, we find that ICT must be accompanied with critical skill education as well as structural changes to the curriculum (Vrasidas et al., 2009) and this is still the largest challenge Melilla leaders confront.

Our findings reveal, despite the internalization of strong and innovative social justice ideologies, Melilla's leaders face limitations to exert changes in their schools' curriculum and ICT infrastructures. These findings lead us to propose that leaders in multicultural contexts have a key role informing the design of social justice programs and public policy. Yet, in Melilla's minority-majority schools, leaders often lack the necessary authority to affect changes in executive policies that can transform their pedagogical practices or curriculums. Based on the legislative guidelines of the Spanish education system, these leaders have moderate autonomy over their local schools; however, as the narratives reveal, Melilla's geographical remoteness, away from Spain's mainland, limits their bargaining power with the central Ministry of Education, in Madrid. Their limited authority is exacerbated by work overloads, given the academic and cultural needs of disadvantaged students and these schools' limited financial support. We mainly find that due to economic and political limitations, minority-majority school leaders in Melilla experience a form of *Symbolic Leadership*.

Overall, Melilla's leaders share common ideologies about the transformation of the curriculum as a main tool for the inclusion and participation of disadvantaged youth, as the earlier works of the lead authors reveal (García-Carmona & García-Quero, 2018). However, this critical pedagogy must be re-oriented toward a flexible curriculum, one which reduces inequality and exclusion based on the intersectionality of gender, race, and ethnic differences, among others (López-Castellano et al., 2019). Our findings suggest an increasing necessity to reach new objectives and standards of leadership in Melilla's schools, given the changing demographics and educational needs of students. As it is already happening with teachers, leaders from Muslim or ethno-racial majority groups should be present in schools and exert authority in the local and Central Educational Ministry as a form of social justice leadership. The results support the recommendations by Santamaría et al. (2014) that minority leaders' identities and their use of culturally relevant pedagogical approaches, may result in effective, equitable leadership outcomes that increase the participation and empowerment of students. We hope the findings will inform the design of future studies on educational leadership and social justice policies with a "vertical" perspective, where the inclusion and empowerment of leaders within multi-cultural contexts and minority-majority schools are top priorities, for without authority, leaders in minority-majority schools fail at abating inequality, becoming, instead, cogs in the wheel of institutional inequality and exclusion, as members of a new form of *symbolic social justice leadership*.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the participants and principals of the schools in this research in Melilla (CEIP Anselmo Pardo, CEIP Gabriel de Morales, CEIP Hipódromo, CEIP Juan Caro, CEIP Constitución y CEIP Real) for their time, accessibility, and interest. We would like also to express our gratitude to the special issue coordinators, and the referees of the article. Their careful reading and insightful comments have greatly helped to improve the quality of our contribution.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Funding

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

ORCID

Marina García-Carmona <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5314-5639>

Norma Fuentes-Mayorga <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-1451-9973>

Antonio-Manuel Rodríguez-García <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-3394-2777>

References

- Aguado, O. V., Borrero, M. A. F., & Pérez, P. A. (2014). La aportación de los grados de desarrollo de la sensibilidad y competencia intercultural. Perspectiva comparada entre Trabajo Social y Psicología. *Cuadernos de Trabajo Social*, 27(2), 307–317. https://doi.org/10.5209/rev_CUTS.2014.v27.n2.44679
- Ainscow, M., & West, M. (2008). *Mejorar las escuelas urbanas: Liderazgo y colaboración* (Vol. 112). Narcea Ediciones.
- Alba, R., & Foner, N. (2015). Mixed unions and immigrant-group integration in North America and Western Europe. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 662(1), 38–56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716215594611>
- Alba, R., & Holdaway, J. (Eds.). (2013). *The children of immigrants at school: A comparative look at integration in the United States and Western Europe*. NYU Press.
- Angelle, P. S. (2017). Beliefs and behaviors of two high school principals in developing a sense of school community for students. *NASSP Bulletin*, 101(1), 5–22. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192636517694957>
- Arar, K., Örücü, D., & Ak Küçükçayır, G. (2020). A holistic look at education of the Syrians under temporary protection in Turkey: Policy, leadership and practice. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*, 23(1), 7–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13603124.2019.1603401>
- Arar, K., Örücü, D., & Ak Küçükçayır, G. (2019). Culturally relevant school leadership for Syrian refugee students in challenging circumstances. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 47(6), 960–979. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143218775430>
- Banks, J. A. (1993). Multicultural education: Historical development, dimensions, and practice. *Review of Research in Education*, 19(1), 3–49. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0091732X019001003>
- Bardin, L. (1996). *Análisis de contenido*. Akal.
- Bass, B. M. (1981). *Stogdill's handbook of leadership*. Free Press.
- Blackmore, J. (2006). Social justice and the study and practice of leadership in education: A feminist history. *Journal of Educational Administration and History*, 38(2), 185–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00220620600554876>
- Bogotch, I. (2002). Educational leadership and social justice: Practice into theory. *Journal of School Leadership*, 12(2), 138–156. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105268460201200203>
- Bogotch, I. (2015). What is social justice leadership? In D. Griffiths & J. P. Portelli (Eds.), *Key questions for educational leaders*. (pp. 131–135). Works & Dees Publishing and Edphil.
- Brooks, J. S., Normore, A. H., & Wilkinson, J. (2017). School leadership, social justice and immigration: Examining, exploring and extending two frameworks. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 31(5), 679–690. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJEM-12-2016-0263>
- Burrello, L. C., Lashley, C., & Beatty, E. E. (2001). *Educating all students together: How school leaders create unified systems*. Corwin Press.
- Camilleri, C. (1992). From multicultural to intercultural: how to move from one to the other. In Lynch, J., Modgil, C. & Modgil, S. (Eds.), *Cultural Diversity and The Schools. Education for Cultural Diversity: Convergence and Divergence* Vol 1. (pp. 141-151). London: The Falmer Press..
- Campos-Soto, A., Aznar, I., Rodríguez-García, A. M., & Rodríguez, C. (2018). Perceptions of shared leadership through ICT in secondary schools in the city of Melilla. In P. Novais, J. J. Jung, J. G. Villarubia, A. Fernández-Caballero, E. Navarro, P. González, D. Caneiro, A. Pinto, & A. T. Campbell (Eds.), *International symposium on ambient intelligence* (pp. 208–215). Springer.
- Carter, P. L. (2010). Race and cultural flexibility among students in different multiracial schools. *Teachers College Record*, 112(6), 1529–1574.

- Crul, M., Holdaway, J., De Valk, H., Fuentes, N., & Zaal, M. (2014). Educating the children of immigrants in old and new Amsterdam. In R. Alba & J. Holdaway (Eds.), *The children of immigrants at school: A comparative look at integration in the United States and Western Europe* (pp. 39–83). New York University Press.
- Crul, M., Schneider, J., & Lelie, F. (Eds.). (2012). *The European second generation compared: Does the integration context matter?* Amsterdam University Press.
- Dantley, M. E., & Tillman, L. C. (2006). Social justice and moral transformative leadership. In C. Marshall & M. Oliva (Eds.), *Leadership for social justice: Making revolutions in education* (pp. 16–30). Pearson Education.
- Fuentes-Mayorga, N. (2012, December 18–20). *Plenary Speaker, “La escuela intercultural: Programas avanzados en Estados Unidos”* Presented at the “XII Congreso interuniversitario de Organización de Instituciones Educativas”, Granada, Spain: Departamento de Didáctica y Organización Escolar, Facultad de Ciencias de la Educación. Universidad de Granada.
- García Carmona, M. (2015). La educación actual: Retos para el profesorado. *Revista Ibe-ro-Americana De Estudos Em Educação*, 10(4), 1199–1211. <https://doi.org/10.21723/riaee.v10i4.8262>
- García-Carmona, M., Evangelou, M., & Fuentes-Mayorga, N. (2020). ‘Hard-to-reach’ parents: Immigrant families’ participation in schools and the views of parent association leaders in Spain and the United States. *Research Papers in Education*, 35(3), 337–358. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2019.1568532>
- García-Carmona, M. (2014). *Análisis de las percepciones sobre liderazgo y participación de las familias en asociaciones de madres y padres en contextos multiculturales* Un estudio comparativo entre Nueva York y Granada [PhD diss.]. University of Granada.
- García-Carmona, M., & García-Quero, F. (2018). Beyond Mo and PoMo: Trans-education for living well in a sustainable world. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 50(14), 1494–1495. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2018.1461434>
- Gibson, M. A., & Carrasco, S. (2009). The education of immigrant youth: Some lessons from the US and Spain. *Theory into Practice*, 48(4), 249–257. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00405840903188118>
- Glaser, B. G., & Strauss, A. L. (1967). *The discovery of grounded theory: Strategies for qualitative research*. Aldine.
- Gómez-Hurtado, I. (2014). El Equipo Directivo como Promotor de Buenas Prácticas para la Justicia Social: Hacia un Liderazgo Inclusivo. *Revista Internacional de Educación para la Justicia Social (RIEJS)*, 3(2), 141–159. <https://revistas.uam.es/riejs/article/view/343>
- Gooden, M. A., & O’Doherty, A. (2015). Do you see what I see? Fostering aspiring leaders’ racial awareness. *Urban Education*, 50(2), 225–255. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085914534273>
- Gundara, J. S., & Sharma, N. (2010). Providing access to education: Intercultural and knowledge issues in the curriculum. In D. Mattheou (Ed.), *Changing educational landscapes* (pp. 93–105). Springer.
- Hajisoteriou, C., & Angelides, P. (2014). Facing the ‘challenge’ school leadership in intercultural schools. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(4_suppl), 65–82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143213502194>
- Horsford, S. D., Grosland, T., & Gunn, K. M. (2011). Pedagogy of the personal and professional: Toward a framework for culturally relevant leadership. *Journal of School Leadership*, 21(4), 582–606. <https://doi.org/10.1177/105268461102100404>
- INE. (2017). *España en cifras*. Instituto Nacional de Estadística. https://www.ine.es/prodyser/espa_cifras/2017/files/assets/common/downloads/publication.pdf
- Instituto de las Culturas de Melilla. (2019). <https://institutodelasculturas.com/>
- James, E. (2001). Learning to bridge the digital divide. *Organization for Economic Cooperation & Development* (p. 224). The OECD Observer.
- Johnson, L. S. (2006). “Making her community a better place to live”: Culturally responsive urban school leadership in historical context. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 5(1), 19–36. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700760500484019>
- Khalifa, M. A., Gooden, M. A., & Davis, J. E. (2016). Culturally responsive school leadership: A synthesis of the literature. *Review of Educational Research*, 86(4), 1272–1311. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543166630383>
- King, F., & Travers, J. (2017). Social justice leadership through the lens of ecological systems theory. In P. S. Angelle (Ed.), *A global perspective of social justice leadership for school principals* (pp. 147–165). Information Age Publishing.
- Lareau, A. (2002). Invisible inequality: Social class and childrearing in black families and white families. *American Sociological Review*, 67(5), 747–776. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3088916>
- Leithwood, K., & Riehl, C. (2005). What we know about successful school leadership. In W. Firestone & C. Riehl (Eds.), *A new agenda: Directions for research on educational leadership* (pp. 22–47). Teachers College Press.
- López, A. E. (2016). *Culturally responsive and socially just leadership in diverse contexts*. Palgrave MacMillan.
- López-Castellano, F., García-Quero, F., & García-Carmona, M. (2019). Perspectives on human and social capital theories and the role of education: An approach from Mediterranean thought. *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, 51(1), 51–62. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2018.1449106>
- Lumby, J., & Coleman, M. (2010). Leadership and diversity. *School Leadership and Management*, 30(1), 1–2. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13632430903509691>
- Marmolejo, J. A., & Montero-Alonso, M. Á. (2009). Statistical and comparative analysis of education in Melilla (Spain). *Investigación Operacional*, 30(2), 149–155. <http://docplayer.net/16226552-Revista-investigacion-operacional-vol-30-no-2-149-155-2009.html>

- MECD. (2017). *Informe 2017 sobre el estado del sistema educativo*. Curso 2015–2016. Secretaría General Técnica. <http://www.cece.es/ftp/recursos/i2017cee.pdf>
- Méndez-Morse, S. (2000). Claiming forgotten leadership. *Urban Education*, 35(5), 584–596. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0042085900355008>
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded source book* (2nd ed.). Sage.
- Miller, P., Roofe, C., & García-Carmona, M. (2019). School leadership, curriculum diversity, social justice and critical perspectives in education. In P. S. Angelle & D. Torrance (Eds.), *Cultures of social justice leadership: An intercultural context of schools* (pp. 93–119). Palgrave MacMillan.
- Ministerio de Educación y Formación Profesional. (2019). *Informe 2019 sobre el estado del sistema educativo*. Ceuta y Melilla. Curso 2017-2018. <http://www.educacionyfp.gob.es/dam/jcr:fc2aa396-6bad-4bef-8576-d2b787f2da11/i19cee10-ceuta-melilla.pdf>
- Morato, J., Ruiz-Robles, A., Sánchez-Cuadrado, S., & Marzal, M. A. (2020). Technologies for digital inclusion: Good practices dealing with diversity. In M. Khosrow-Pour et al. (Eds.), *Information Resources Management Association, Wealth Creation and Poverty Reduction: Breakthroughs in Research and Practice* (pp. 17–37). IGI Global.
- Murillo, F. J. (2006). Una dirección escolar para el cambio: Del liderazgo transformacional al liderazgo distribuido. *REICE. Revista Iberoamericana de Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*, 4(4), 12–24. <http://hdl.handle.net/10486/660840>
- Murillo, F. J. M., & Hernández-Castilla, R. (2011). Hacia un concepto de justicia social. *REICE. Revista Iberoamericana sobre Calidad, Eficacia y Cambio en Educación*, 9(4), 7–23. <http://hdl.handle.net/10486/660840>
- Normore, A. H., & Brooks, J. S. (Eds.). (2014). *Educational leadership for ethics and social justice: Views from the social sciences*. Information Age Publishing.
- OECD. (2010). *International migration outlook, 2010*.
- OECD. (2012). *International migration outlook 2012*.
- Portes, A., & Rumbaut, R. G. (2001). *Legacies: The story of the immigrant second generation*. University of California Press.
- Portes, A., & Rumbaut, R. G. (2005). Introduction: The second generation and the children of immigrants longitudinal study. *Ethnic and Racial Studies*, 28(6), 983–999. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01419870500224109>
- Robinson, K. K. (2017). Retracing the steps of the journey: A literature review of social justice leadership from a global context. In P. Angelle (Ed.), *A global perspective of social justice leadership for school principals* (pp. 21–41). Information Age Publishing.
- Roth, F., & Thum, A. E. (2010). *The key role of education in the Europe 2020 strategy* (CEPS Working Document 338). Centre for European Policy Studies.
- Santamaría, L. J., Santamaría, A. P., & Dam, L. I. (2014). Liderazgo Crítico Aplicado a través de Lentes Latinas: Un Enfoque Alternativo de Liderazgo Educativo. *Revista Internacional de Educación para la Justicia Social*, 3(2), 161–180. <https://revistas.uam.es/riejs/article/view/344>
- Sarid, A. (2019). Social justice dilemmas: A multidimensional framework of social justice educational leadership. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15700763.2019.1631856>
- Shapiro, J. P., & Stefkovich, J. A. (2016). *Ethical leadership and decision making in education: Applying theoretical perspectives to complex dilemmas*. Routledge.
- Shields, C. M. (2014). Leadership for social justice education: A critical transformative approach. In I. Bogotch & C. M. Shields (Eds.), *International handbook of educational leadership and social (in)justice* (pp. 323–339). Dordrecht: Springer.
- Taysum, A., & Gunter, H. (2008). A critical approach to researching social justice and school leadership in England. *Education, Citizenship and Social Justice*, 3(2), 183–199. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17461979080900083>
- Telles, E. E., & Ortiz, V. (2008). *Generations of exclusion: Mexican-Americans, assimilation, and race*. Russell Sage Foundation.
- Theoharis, G. (2007). Social justice educational leaders and resistance: Toward a theory of social justice leadership. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 43(2), 221–258. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X06293717>
- Tójar, J. C. (2006). *Investigación cualitativa. Comprender y actuar*. La Muralla.
- Vilà, R. (2006). La dimensión afectiva de la competencia comunicativa intercultural en la Educación Secundaria Obligatoria: Escala de Sensibilidad Intercultural. *Revista de Investigación Educativa*, 24(2), 353–372. <https://revistas.um.es/rie/article/view/96891>
- Vrasidas, C., Zembylas, M., & Glass, G. V. (2009). *ICT for education, development and social justice*. Information Age Publishing, Inc.
- Wade, J. M., Bean, A., & Teixeira-Poit, S. (2019). Students, universities and employers: Why we all win when we promote social justice through SoTL. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 13(3), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.20429/ijstol.2019.130302>
- White, R. E., Cooper, K., & Mackey, W. (2014). Culturally relevant education and critical pedagogy: Devolution of hierarchies of power. *Revista Internacional de Educación para la Justicia Social*, 3(2), 123–140. <https://revistas.uam.es/riejs/article/view/342>

- Willems, J. (2019). Digital equity: Considering the needs of staff as a social justice issue. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 35(6), 150–160. <https://doi.org/10.14742/ajet.5503>
- Ylimaki, R. M., Jacobson, S. L., & Drysdale, L. (2007). Making a difference in challenging, high-poverty schools: Successful principals in the USA, England, and Australia. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*, 18(4), 361–381. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243450701712486>